

Density and Museum Relevance: A Multi-Speed Cultural Italy

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- Strong territorial imbalances persist, with the Center-North dominant and the Mezzogiorno (Southern Italy) still penalized in terms of museum relevance.
- The pandemic marks a structural break, with uneven recoveries and incomplete returns to pre-2020 levels.
- Smaller regions show dynamism, thanks to local valorization, proximity tourism, and targeted cultural strategies.

The analysis of data on the density and relevance of regional museum heritage in the period 2017–2022 paints a complex and highly differentiated picture of the Italian museum system. The value of the indicator, which synthesizes the presence and importance of museum heritage in relation to the territory, clearly highlights both the historical concentration of museums in certain regions and the structural difficulties of other areas of the country. The period considered is also marked by a strong discontinuity represented by the Covid-19 pandemic, which significantly affected museum attendance and operations, with effects that were not always homogeneous.

In Northern Italy, the situation appears generally solid, albeit not without fluctuations. Lombardy represents the case of greatest stability: values remain consistently around 1.5 throughout the entire period, with no overall change between 2017 and 2022. This figure points to a well-structured museum system, resilient to external shocks and capable of recovering quickly after the contraction of 2020. A similar dynamic, though with greater volatility, can be observed in Veneto, which moves from 2.01 in 2017 to a peak of 2.40 in 2018, then declines in 2020 and rises again to 1.93 in 2022. The slight final decrease (-3.98%) does not undermine the region's central role in the national cultural landscape.

Piedmont and Emilia-Romagna, by contrast, show more mixed trajectories. Piedmont records a slight overall contraction (-5.93%), with values fluctuating around 1.1 and a partial recovery in 2021. Emilia-Romagna, on the other hand, closes the period with a positive balance (+8.41%), a sign of a good capacity for relaunch after the 2020 downturn. More critical is the situation in Liguria and Friuli-Venezia Giulia, both characterized by significant reductions of -28.35% and -21.19% respectively. In these cases, the 2020 collapse is not fully recovered in the following years, suggesting structural fragilities or difficulties in repositioning the museum offer.

A particularly interesting case is that of Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol, which, despite starting from average values, records a significant decline in 2022 (-18.35% compared to 2017). This trend may be linked to a strong dependence on international tourism, which was drastically reduced during and after the pandemic, with direct effects on the perceived relevance of the museum system.

Turning to Central Italy, strong polarizations emerge. Tuscany and Lazio confirm themselves as the regions with the highest values in the entire country, testifying to an exceptional concentration of museum assets of national and international importance. However, both record a decline over the period considered: Tuscany falls from 3.87 to 3.28 (-15.25%), while Lazio drops from 7.20 to 6.13 (-14.86%). In particular, Lazio shows a very sharp drop in 2020, linked to the closure of major museum hubs and the drastic reduction in tourist flows, followed by only a partial recovery in 2022. This suggests that territories with a strong dependence on international cultural tourism were also those most exposed to exogenous shocks.

Alongside these leading regions, Central Italy also presents cases of unexpected dynamism. Umbria, although starting from low values, shows an overall increase of +27.78%, with a significant peak in 2021. This trend can be interpreted as the result of local valorization policies and greater attention to

proximity tourism, which favored less congested regions. The Marche, by contrast, remain essentially stable, with a minimal change (+3.45%), a sign of a museum system that holds up but struggles to make a structural leap forward.

In Southern Italy and the Islands, the situation appears more problematic and fragmented. Campania and Sicily represent the main exceptions, with relatively high values compared to the southern average. Campania maintains levels above 3 throughout the period, although it closes with a slight reduction (-4.68%). Sicily, on the other hand, records a more marked decline (-12%), indicating difficulty in consolidating the progress made in previous years. In both cases, the very high cultural potential has not yet fully translated into stable growth in museum relevance.

The other southern regions show very low values and, in most cases, declining trends. Apulia, Calabria, and Basilicata record significant percentage decreases of -37.84%, -27.27%, and -18.75% respectively. These figures point to a persistent structural weakness of the museum system, linked to factors such as fragmentation of the offer, lack of investment, and limited integration with national tourist and cultural circuits. An exception is Abruzzo, which, while maintaining very low absolute values, records the highest percentage increase (+30.77%). Here too, the increase should be read in light of a base effect: small improvements produce high percentage variations without substantially changing the region's positioning.

A separate discussion is warranted for the smaller regions. Valle d'Aosta shows a decidedly positive trend (+28.32%), with steady growth after 2018. This result suggests that in small territories, with a well-defined museum offer integrated into the tourism context, it is possible to strengthen cultural relevance even in times of crisis. Molise, by contrast, shows strong fluctuations and closes with a negative balance (-14.29%), confirming the difficulties of continuity and critical mass that characterize smaller museum systems.

Overall, 2020 represents a clear watershed for all regions. In almost every case, a drop in the indicator is observed, more or less pronounced, followed by a partial recovery in the following two years. However, only a few regions manage to return to or exceed pre-pandemic levels. This highlights how the health crisis had lasting effects and how the resilience of the museum system depends strongly on diversification of the offer, capacity for innovation, and territorial rootedness.

In conclusion, the data point to a multi-speed museum Italy. On the one hand, regions such as Lazio, Tuscany, Veneto, and Lombardy continue to play a leading role, albeit showing signs of vulnerability. On the other, many southern regions remain behind, despite potentially extraordinary cultural heritage. The positive experiences of regions such as Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, and Emilia-Romagna, however, indicate that targeted policies of valorization, territorial integration, and innovation can produce concrete results. Strengthening the density and relevance of museum heritage therefore appears to be not only a matter of historical endowment, but above all of strategy, governance, and the ability to adapt to economic and social change.

Source: ISTAT

Link: www.istat.it

Regione	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	Var Ass	Var Per
Piemonte	1,18	1,17	1,08	1,05	1,18	1,11	-0,07	-5,93
Valle d'Aosta	1,13	0,97	1,05	1,37	1,38	1,45	0,32	28,32
Liguria	1,27	1,14	1,09	0,68	0,79	0,91	-0,36	-28,35
Lombardia	1,55	1,53	1,61	1,25	1,57	1,55	0,00	0,00
Trentino-Alto Adige	1,09	1,13	1,01	1,16	1,19	0,89	-0,20	-18,35
Veneto	2,01	2,40	2,00	1,49	1,82	1,93	-0,08	-3,98
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	1,51	1,37	1,41	1,36	1,51	1,19	-0,32	-21,19
Emilia-Romagna	1,07	1,09	1,15	0,97	1,21	1,16	0,09	8,41
Toscana	3,87	3,92	3,94	3,35	3,28	3,28	-0,59	-15,25
Umbria	0,72	0,81	0,65	0,87	1,40	0,92	0,20	27,78
Marche	0,58	0,65	0,81	0,94	0,83	0,60	0,02	3,45
Lazio	7,20	6,25	7,20	4,31	4,09	6,13	-1,07	-14,86
Abruzzo	0,13	0,11	0,14	0,16	0,16	0,17	0,04	30,77
Molise	0,14	0,10	0,14	0,25	0,19	0,12	-0,02	-14,29
Campania	3,63	4,24	3,61	3,11	3,58	3,46	-0,17	-4,68
Puglia	0,37	0,31	0,29	0,20	0,27	0,23	-0,14	-37,84
Basilicata	0,16	0,18	0,23	0,18	0,18	0,13	-0,03	-18,75
Calabria	0,33	0,31	0,28	0,25	0,30	0,24	-0,09	-27,27
Sicilia	1,00	1,13	0,97	0,86	1,00	0,88	-0,12	-12,00
Sardegna	0,31	0,35	0,37	0,31	0,39	0,32	0,01	3,23

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